

Magnetic Rotation of Some Salts of Higher Fatty Acids and Evidence in Favour of the Formation of Ionic Micelle.

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Magnetic rotation of the plane of polarisation of various substances like other physical properties, such as electrical conductivity, osmotic pressure, refractive index, surface tension, viscosity, etc., has been extensively studied by Perkin and various other workers. From the measurements, already published, it can be seen that the rotation of salts in solutions is approximately determined additively as the sum of the ions present, if a single substance be present, and is the sum of the components, if more than one substance is there. But there are cases like FeCl_3 in water where magnetic rotation varies with concentration (Becquerel, "Smithsonian Physical Tables," 1908, p. 289; Richards and Roberts, *Phil. Mag.*, 1927, 3, 770) or with temperature (Pillai, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1932, 6, 573). This is attributed by some to the presence of colloidal Fe_2O_3 particles and by others to the ionisation. In order to decide, therefore, which factor is responsible for this deviation, a study of various sols such as Fe_2O_3 , V_2O_5 , SiO_2 , etc., was undertaken but as the technique of the formation of stable concentrated sols of sufficient transparency is yet not quite perfect, the results obtained will be discussed later. But a study of magnetic rotation of soap solutions which contain colloidal particles, ionic micelle, etc., and are known as colloidal electrolytes has been quite accurately carried out and forms the subject of the present investigation. So far the magnetic rotations of sodium oleate and potassium oleate solutions in water and alcohol at different concentrations have been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The salts were prepared in the laboratory by the method advocated by McBain. Alcoholic solution of sodium or potassium hydroxide was added gradually to an alcoholic solution of oleic acid and the neutrality of the mixture was tested by phenolphthalein. The soap was then dried first in an oven maintained at 80° and then in a vacuum desiccator till it was completely free from alcohol.

There are two methods generally employed to investigate the magnetic rotation of the plane of polarisation of different substances. One, used by Perkin consists in placing the substances to be investigated between the pole pieces of an electromagnet. The other method which has been extensively employed in the latter work consists in placing an ordinary polarimeter tube inside a large solenoid. It is the latter method that has been adopted in the present investigation because it gives a sufficient length of the liquid column which is desirable for accurate observation of optical rotations.

The solenoid employed was wound over a "former" of a thin fibre tube, 20 cm. long. This consisted of 44 layers each having sixty-seven turns of No. 14 s.w.g., D.C.C. copper wire. The solenoid was nearly 20 cm. long. The internal diameter of the fibre tube was 3 cm.

The current for the solenoid was obtained from the supply of the mains and was capable of fine adjustment by a sliding rheostat in series with another variable resistance. A Weston precision ammeter was included in the circuit as well. To obtain fairly large rotation angles for measurement, a current of 9.5 amps. was used which corresponds to effects of 992 watts. This naturally caused a rapid heating of the solenoid.

In view of the dependence of rotation on temperature, it is necessary that some arrangement must be made to take the observations at a constant temperature. The polarisation tube used was, therefore, a double jacketed one. Through the outer jacket water was continuously circulated to keep the temperature of the solution constant.

A Hilger polarimeter with Lippich tripartite field was used. This polarimeter ordinarily is provided with a V-shaped carrier for placing observation tubes. This had to be removed and replaced by a suitable board on which was fixed the large solenoid. The source of light used was a glass mercury vapour lamp with a dichromate filter.

In order to calculate the molecular rotation of a dissolved substance from the measured rotation of the solution, it is assumed that the dissolved substance and the solvent act independently of each other, and that the measured rotation is composed additively from the rotation of these two. This assumption leads, therefore, to the following expression for the molecular rotation of the dissolved substance (with molecular rotation of water as 1) when the dissolving medium is water:

$$M = \frac{D_2 (\mu m_1 + m_2)}{D_1 d m_1} - \mu \times M_w$$

where M = molecular rotation of the dissolved substance ;

M_w = " " of the solvent (water = 1) ;

D_2 = measured angle of rotation for solution } with the same layer of thickness, temperature and magnetic field.
 D_1 = measured angle of rotation for water }

m_1 = molecular weight of water ;

m_2 = molecular weight of dissolved substance ;

μ = the number of gram molecules of solvent per gram molecule of the dissolved substance ;

d = density of the solution.

It is to be expected that if the assumption mentioned above does not hold, the molecular rotation will vary with concentration.

When the solvent is not water but alcohol, then firstly the molecular rotation of alcohol is determined by the following expression :

$$m_s = \frac{\gamma_1}{\gamma} \times \frac{M}{d \cdot \times}$$

where γ_1 = rotation of solvent, γ = rotation of water, M = molecular weight of the solvent, m = molecular weight of water, d = density of the solvent, and then the molecular rotation of the solution is calculated by Otto Humbug's formula (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1893, 12, 402),

$$d_m = \frac{w \times M_1 \times 100}{w_{H_2O} \times S \times 18 \times a}$$

where w = rotation of solution, w_{H_2O} = rotation of water, S = density, a = % of the substance present in the solution, M_1 = molecular weight of the solute, M , the molecular rotation of the dissolved substance is then $d_m = m_s$

where d_m is the molecular rotation of the solution and m_s is the molecular rotation of the solvent.

The results obtained are tabulated below.

TABLE I.

Magnetic rotation of sodium oleate in water.

Solution.	m_2 .	a .	μ .	d .	D_2/D_1 .	M .
A	304.25	18.02	77.0	1.0027	1.054	21.8
B	„	13.39	109.4	0.9997	1.033	21.1
C	„	10.89	138.3	0.9995	1.024	20.6
D	„	7.09	221.4	0.9981	1.014	20.5
E	„	5.76	276.6	0.9976	1.017	22.6
F	„	2.96	553.3	0.9966	1.005	21.6

TABLE II.

Magnetic rotation of potassium oleate in water.

Solution.	m_2	a_s	μ .	d .	D_2/D_1 .	M .
A	320.37	13.84	110.8	1.002	1.042	22.4
B	„	11.90	131.8	1.001	1.029	22.6
C	„	7.723	212.7	1.000	1.026	23.6
D	„	5.16	326.6	0.9977	1.019	25.2
E	„	3.24	531.4	0.9960	1.013	27.2

TABLE III.

Magnetic rotation of potassium oleate in alcohol.

Molecular rotation of alcohol = 2.283.

Solution.	M_1 .	a .	μ .	S .	w/w_{H_2O} .	M .
A	320.37	19.35	29.02	0.8333	0.9348	20.47
B	„	18.57	30.54	0.8309	0.9249	20.50
C	„	16.40	35.50	0.8283	0.9241	20.90
D	„	15.01	39.52	0.8247	0.9200	20.70

The % column (a) gives the solution's percentage contents of the stated substances.

DISCUSSION AND SUMMARY.

From the tables it is clear that the magnetic rotation both in the case of potassium and sodium oleates in water varies with concentration and has a maximum value at a concentration of 5.70% in the case of sodium oleate and at 3.2% in the case of potassium oleate. In case of potassium oleate in alcohol, the magnetic rotation is practically constant and the value is 20.67 ± 0.2 .

It has been shown by various workers that the magnetic rotation of various substances in non-ionising media remains constant, but in ionising media great anomalies are exhibited. In some the rotation increases with dilution, in others it decreases with dilution, whereas there are a few in which it remains constant.

The magnetic rotation of potassium oleate in alcohol at different concentrations remains almost constant. It can be assumed, therefore, that potassium oleate does not ionise in alcohol. But as magnetic rotation of aqueous solutions of potassium and sodium oleates varies with concentration it indicates that solute and solvent do not behave independent of each other.

It is well known that at low concentrations these salts behave as crystalloids and as the solutions become concentrated the ions coalesce to form the nucleus of colloidal particles, termed the ionic micelle, which have general formula $(\text{Col})_x (\text{ol})_n^{(n)^1} (\text{H}_2\text{O})_m$. The amount of water of hydration is least in concentrated solutions.

From Table I, it can be seen that in case of sodium oleate, with the increase of concentration the rotation goes on increasing till the concentration acquires a value of 5.76%. After this the rotation begins to fall till a concentration of 10.89% is reached and then it remains practically constant. These variations indicate that soap solutions belong to that class of compounds in which the rotation decreases with dilution.

The whole behaviour can be explained by assuming that in these cases the rotation goes on increasing with the increase of concentration and at the same time ionic micelle are formed which have a lower rotation value. At a concentration of 5.76% the different phases are in equilibrium and after that the concentration of ionic micelle increases with the result that the rotation goes on falling till it reaches a value of 10.89%. Beyond this there are only ionic micelle in the solution. Therefore the rotation value is practically constant.

These results are in accord with the results obtained by McBain, Laing and Titley (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 1279) by a study of changes of electrical conductivity with concentration of these salts. They found the electrical conductivity to be minimum at the concentration where the rotation obtained by us is maximum and to be maximum where the rotation is minimum.

Further work on other allied salts is in progress and the results will be communicated later on.

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